

High abundances of ammonia-oxidizing archaea in nitrifying biofilters of brackish recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) with tolerance for abrupt salinity changes

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ABSTRACT

While bacterial diversity is heavily studied in recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), little is known about how nitrifying communities differ across commercial biofilters operated at varying salinities. This particularly applies to ammonia-oxidizing microbes, as most studies have not been designed to target archaea and comammox *Nitrospira*. Furthermore, the relationship between the composition of these nitrifying communities and their tolerance to salinity changes remains understudied. The overall aim of this study was to clarify the relationship between the composition of the nitrifying communities and the salinity tolerance of nitrifying biofilters in commercial RAS. The objectives were to (i) assess the immediate tolerance of brackish and seawater biofilters subjected to abrupt and large salinity changes, (ii) evaluate the temporal dynamics of microbial communities in the biofilter-biofilm during operational changes, and (iii) determine the relative abundances of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA), and complete ammonia oxidizers (comammox *Nitrospira*) in RAS biofilters operated at different salinities. Microbial communities were characterized using 16S rRNA gene amplicon and shotgun sequencing. We found that the brackish biofilter was relatively tolerant to abrupt and large salinity changes, with reductions in nitrification capacity of around 16 % and 22 % after exposure to freshwater (0 ppt) and seawater (31 ppt), respectively, and the seawater biofilter declined by around 50 % when exposed to freshwater (0 ppt). We observed an increasing similarity in microbial community composition between the donor and recipient biofilters, suggesting that biofilter seeding can foster the establishment of robust nitrifying consortia. This may help accelerate biofilter start-up in RAS. The RAS operated at high salinity had a higher relative abundance of AOA than the freshwater RAS. Furthermore, the relative abundance of comammox *Nitrospira* was high in the freshwater RAS but undetectable in the brackish and seawater systems. Stable and ammonia-poor conditions in RAS appeared to select microbes physiologically adapted with high affinities to ammonia, such as AOA and comammox *Nitrospira*.

1. Introduction

Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) rely on nitrifying biofilters to facilitate the microbial conversion of toxic ammonia into nitrate, a process known as nitrification. One of the challenges in operating RAS is to obtain and maintain an efficient nitrification, especially in marine systems. Seawater biofilters typically take longer to start up than freshwater biofilters (Burut-Archanai et al., 2021; Keuter et al., 2017). Moreover, higher or fluctuating salinity often reduces the nitrification capacity by inhibiting the activity of microorganisms due to osmotic stress (Zhang et al., 2023). Salinity fluctuations can occur in RAS for

various reasons, such as control failure, natural salinity variation of the intake water, or as a strategy in farm operations - for instance, in transitioning anadromous species (e.g., Atlantic salmon), and combating pathogens or parasites in the system (Boylan et al., 2021; Mifsud and Rowland, 2008). As brackish and seawater RAS are increasingly used to produce larger Atlantic salmon smolt, research is required to improve our understanding of biofiltration at higher and fluctuating salinity.

The nitrification capacity of the biofilter heavily depends on the composition of the microbial communities within the biofilter-biofilm. Despite the importance of these microbial communities, their adaptability to environmental perturbations, such as changes in salinity,

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remains poorly understood. The biofilter microbial communities can exhibit resilience to salinity changes (Navada and Vadstein, 2022); however, the role of specific nitrifiers under varying salinity conditions requires further investigation. Previous studies documented several nitrifier groups in RAS biofilters. *Nitrosomonas* spp. (ammonia-oxidizing bacteria; AOB) and *Nitrospira* spp. (nitrite-oxidizing bacteria, NOB) are commonly present in freshwater RAS biofilters (Bartelme et al., 2017; Dahle et al., 2023). In addition, *Nitrospira* species with the ability to perform complete nitrification from ammonia to nitrate, i.e., comammox (Ca. *Nitrospira nitrificans* and Ca. *N. inopinata*), have also been described (Daims et al., 2015; Van Kessel et al., 2015).

Among the nitrifying microbes, AOB and NOB have received the most attention. Most studies of nitrifying communities in RAS biofilters have been based on sequencing of bacterial 16S rRNA gene amplicons. Some studies noticed a low abundance of AOB (Dahle et al., 2023). Other ammonia-oxidizing groups, such as ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA) and comammox, may be important to nitrification but remain undetected because of methodological issues. “Universal” polymerase chain reaction (PCR) primers for 16S rRNA gene may not target archaeal species (Youngblut et al., 2021), and comammox bacteria cannot be distinguished from NOB based on partial 16S rRNA gene sequences (Daims et al., 2016). Earlier studies have shown that archaeal communities can be a significant nitrifier in RAS, but their presence is often overlooked and underinvestigated (Moschos et al., 2022). For instance, quantifying the *amoA* gene has revealed a higher abundance of AOA than AOB in the nitrifying biofilter of freshwater RAS (Bartelme et al., 2017; Khangembam et al., 2017). Meanwhile, several other studies did not find a substantial presence of AOA, indicating the opposite (Foesel et al., 2008; Hüpeden et al., 2020; Roalkvam et al., 2020). Thus, the contribution of AOA in ammonia oxidation in the RAS biofilter is unclear and requires further investigation.

In this study, we investigated the immediate tolerance of commercial RAS biofilters operated at brackish and seawater salinities (15 and 35 ppt) to abrupt and large salinity changes. We observed a noticeable tolerance of these biofilters. To further investigate this finding, we extended the study by sampling biofilters from freshwater RAS as a comparison and analyzing the composition of the nitrifying communities, with particular emphasis on ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA) and bacteria (AOB). Overall, our aim was to improve the knowledge about the relationship between the nitrifying community composition at varying salinities and the salinity tolerance of biofilters in commercial RAS. The objectives were to (i) assess the nitrification capacity and immediate tolerance of brackish and seawater biofilters subjected to abrupt and large salinity changes, (ii) evaluate the temporal dynamics of microbial communities during operational changes, and (iii) determine the relative abundances of AOB, AOA, and complete ammonia oxidizers (comammox *Nitrospira*) to the ammonia oxidation in RAS operated at different salinities using 16S rRNA gene amplicon and shotgun sequencing.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Description of RAS facilities, biofilters, and sample collection

This study investigated the nitrifying community in the biofilter-biofilm from three commercial RAS facilities: Havland RAS Pilot AS, Erko Seafood AS, and Lerøy Seafood AS. An overview of the characteristics of the RAS facilities and their biofilter biomedica is given in Table 1.

At Havland’s RAS, the biofilter was started in January 2021 at 25 ppt salinity using a small fraction of biofilter biomedica sourced from biofilters operated at Erko Seafood AS as seed, see Tesdal (2021). In June 2022, the production of salmon at Havland’s RAS was stopped. The salinity in the facility was then gradually increased to 35 ppt, and the biofilter was fed with ammonium before being used for Atlantic cod production from August 2022. To monitor the temporal development of microbial community of Havland RAS biofilter, biomedica were collected twice before transitioning from salmon production (on April 26 and May 10, 2022) and multiple times during the initial stages of cod production at 35 ppt salinity (on September 2, 8 and 26; then October 12; November 16, and 27, all in 2022).

At Erko Seafood AS, the facility was started in 2017 at 25 ppt salinity for producing Atlantic salmon smolts. By the time of our sampling (October 14, 2022), the salinity at Erko’s RAS had changed to 15 ppt (brackish). To compare the nitrifying biofilm communities of the biofilters of RAS operated at various salinities, we expanded the study to include samples from freshwater RAS biofilters. We sampled both moving-bed and fixed-bed biofilters from two independent commercial-scale freshwater RAS (operated at a salinity below three ppt) used to produce Atlantic salmon smolts at Lerøy Midt AS, Hemne. The fixed-bed biofilters were positioned upstream of the moving-bed biofilters, and they had been running for more than ten years without disinfection. In addition, a fixed-bed biofilter in RAS for post-smolt production operated at 22 ppt for around two years at the same facility was sampled.

2.2. Determination of the ammonium removal capacity of biomedica at different salinities

To assess the salinity tolerance, the ammonium (NH₄-N) removal capacity of the biomedica from Havland and Erko biofilters was evaluated at different salinities by performing short-term batch experiments (Fig. 1). The selected test salinities were 0, 15, and 31 ppt to impose a significant shift relative to the original salinity for all biomedica groups. The biomedica from Havland and Erko were collected on September 26 and October 14, 2022, respectively, and were shipped on ice overnight to NTNU’s lab. Upon arrival, to avoid starvation and biofilm detachment, the biomedica were incubated overnight at room temperature (~21 °C) in ammonium medium at a concentration of around 7.5 mg/L (given in Appendix A) with a salinity identical to their biofilter origin (35 and 15 ppt for the Havland and Erko biomedica, respectively). The next day, the biomedica were incubated for 24 h in the ammonium medium at the relevant test salinity (0, 15, or 31 ppt) to physiologically adapt the biofilms to a new salinity. The next day, the ammonium removal capacity of the biomedica was determined in batch reactors of 1 L filled with 350 mL biomedica and 600 mL ammonium medium at the

Table 1

Overview of the characteristics of RAS facilities, their biofilter biomedica specifications investigated in this study, and the number of samples collected for microbial community characterization using 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing.

No	RAS biofilters	Species	Salinity	Type of biofilter*	Samples	Biomedica model	Number / m ³	Specific surface area (m ² /m ³)
1	Havland	Salmon	Brackish, 25 ppt	MBBF	6	Saddle chips (RK BioElements, DK)	255,000	750
		Cod	Seawater, 35 ppt	MBBF	18			
2	Erko	Salmon	Brackish, 15 ppt	FBBF	3	BTW15 (Biowater Technology, USA)	640,000	823
3	Lerøy	Salmon	Freshwater, <3 ppt	MBBF & FBBF	24	RK Bioelements (RK BioElements, DK)	255,000	750
		Salmon	Brackish, 22 ppt	FBBF	5			

* MBBF = moving-bed biofilter, FBBF = fixed-bed biofilter.

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the experimental design for determining nitrification capacity at different salinities. The procedure was performed for carriers from both Havland and Erko. On day 1, the biomedia were incubated at the original salinity.

corresponding test salinity, 0, 15, or 31 ppt (Fig. 1). To ensure that both biomedia types had an equal surface area, the number of biomedia pieces was adjusted: 200 pieces for Erko and 80 pieces for Havland, corresponding to a total surface area of 0.257 m². A magnetic stirrer was used to ensure proper mixing and aeration of the reactors. To determine NH₄-N and nitrite (NO₂-N) concentrations, 2 mL samples were collected and filtered through a 0.2 μm PES syringe filter (Sarstedt, DE) at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 min after the batch experiments started. The samples were kept on ice during the experiment and then stored at -20 °C until analyzed using the Hach-Lange cuvette kit (LCK305 and LCK339) according to the manufacturer's instructions on the DR3900 spectrophotometer (HACH®, DE). The raw data showing the ammonium and nitrite measurements at each sampling point are provided in Supplementary File S1.

Surface-specific ammonium removal capacity (SST), expressed as g N m⁻² day⁻¹, was calculated using the formula in Eq. (1) (Kinyage et al., 2019).

$$SST \text{ (g N m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{S \times V_w \times 60 \text{ (min h}^{-1}\text{)} \times 24 \text{ (h d}^{-1}\text{)}}{A_m \times 1000 \text{ (mg g}^{-1}\text{)}} \quad (1)$$

Where: S is the volumetric ammonium degradation rate (mg N L⁻¹ min⁻¹); V_w is the volume of medium in the reactor (L); and A_m is the total surface area of the biomedia (m²).

Linear regression ($y = a + bx$) was performed to determine the volumetric ammonium removal rate (S), which is equal to the negative of the slope b, where y is the ammonium concentration (mg/L) in the reactor, x is the time, and a is the intercept. We aimed to determine the maximum ammonium removal capacity, i.e., representing a situation where the substrate is not limiting the conversion rate; therefore, only data points in the linear region of the curve were included.

2.3. Bacterial community characterization using 16S rRNA gene amplicon and shotgun sequencing

2.3.1. DNA extraction and 16S rRNA gene amplicon library preparation

For the characterization of microbial biofilm communities, pieces of

plastic biomedia from the moving-bed biofilters were collected, while for fixed-bed biofilters, microbial biomass was collected either by swabbing the biofilter top or collecting sludge during biofilter back-wash. Triplicate samples, i.e., three separate plastic biomedia pieces, cotton swabs, or portions of sludge, were taken for each sampling time (detailed in Table 1). All samples were stored at -20 °C upon collection, shipped on ice overnight, and stored at -20 °C until processed. The biomedia from moving-bed biofilters were cut into a quarter piece and used as input to the DNA extraction. For the fixed-bed biofilters, the swab cotton tip and the pelleted sludge after centrifugation were used. Samples were loaded into tubes containing lysis solution and homogenized using a Precellys 24 Tissue Homogenizer (Bertin Technologies, FRA) at 5500 rpm for two 30-s cycles. Then, DNA was extracted using MagAttract Powersoil® Pro DNA kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) for samples collected from brackish and seawater RAS or ZymoBIOMICS 96 MagBead DNA kit (Zymo Research, USA) for samples from freshwater RAS, with a semi-automatic platform, KingFisher Flex Purification System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Bacterial and archaeal communities in biofilm samples were characterized using 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing. The V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified with Illumina adapter-linked primers. For bacteria, primers Ill-345F (5'-CCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG-3') and Ill-805R (5'-GACTACNVGGGTATCTAAKCC-3') were used, while for targeting archaea, primers Ill-A340F (5'-CCCTAYGGGGYGCASCAG-3') and Ill-A760R (5'-GGACTACCSGGGTATCTAATCC-3') (Nordgård et al., 2017) were used. PCR reactions, with a total volume of 25 μL, consisted of 1 μL of a DNA extract as the template (undiluted or 1:10 diluted), 0.2 mM of each dNTP (VWR), 0.3 μM of each primer, 0.02 units/μL of Phusion HS DNA polymerase, and 1× HF Phusion buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The cycling conditions were 98 °C for 2 min, followed by 36 thermocycles (98 °C for 15 s, 55 °C for 20 s, 72 °C for 20 s), and a final extension at 72 °C for 5 min. Amplicons were first assessed using 1 % agarose gel electrophoresis before being normalized and purified using the SequalPrep Normalization Plate Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) following the kit protocol. Next, the amplicons were combinatorially dual-indexed using Nextera XT Index Kit v2 (Illumina, Inc., USA). Indexing PCRs were performed with a similar reagent concentration as above, except 2.5 μL of normalized PCR product was used as the template with 10 thermocycles (98 °C for 5 s, 50 °C for 20 s, and 72 °C for 20 s). All PCRs were carried out in a T100™ Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., USA). The indexed amplicons were assessed using gel electrophoresis and then normalized and purified as previously described. The libraries were pooled and concentrated using the Amicon® Ultra 0.5 mL Centrifugal Filters 30 k (Merck & Co., Inc., USA) and were quality-checked using agarose gel electrophoresis and the NanoDrop One (Thermo Fisher, USA). Three sets of amplicon libraries were prepared with 68, 42, and 96 samples in each set, where the last set included 30 samples not relevant to this study. The amplicon libraries were paired-end sequenced (2 × 300 bp) on three separate runs using an Illumina MiSeq sequencer at the Norwegian Sequencing Centre (NSC) with MiSeq Reagent Kit v3 (Illumina Inc., USA). The sequencing data are available at the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) with accession number PRJNA1274364. The metadata for each sequencing library, describing the sampling location, salinity, primers, and other relevant information, is provided in Supplementary File S2.

2.3.2. Processing of amplicon sequencing data

The amplicon sequencing reads were processed using USEARCH v.11 (Edgar, 2010). In brief, the reads were truncated at the first base where the quality score (Q) dropped below 30. The reads were merged and reads shorter than 380 bp were discarded. The primer binding sequences were stripped, and the merged reads were quality-filtered and de-duplicated to obtain unique sequences using the default settings. Denoising, i.e., predicting the true biological sequence (amplicon sequence variants; ASVs) from these unique sequences, was performed

using Unoise3 (Edgar, 2016a). The chimeric sequences and sequences with fewer than eight reads among all samples were removed in the denoising process. Merged reads were mapped to ASVs to obtain the read counts for each sample. The taxonomic classification for the obtained ASVs was predicted using the SINTAX classifier (Edgar, 2016b) with the RDP training set v19 (Wang and Cole, 2024) as the reference database. The ASVs representing non-bacterial taxa were removed, e.g., chloroplasts, eukaryotes, and taxa of known kit contaminants detected upon inspection in the extraction controls. Only samples with $\geq 24,839$ reads were used. The sequence processing resulted in an ASV table comprising 111 samples with a median read depth of 118,744. We filtered ASVs by the string “Nitr” to flag putative nitrifiers and then manually verified the results. To describe the nitrifying bacterial community, the archaeal ASVs were excluded from the dataset generated using a primer pair that is more selective for bacteria. Similarly, bacterial ASVs were excluded from the dataset generated using a primer pair that was more selective for archaea.

2.3.3. Phylogenetic analysis of major nitrifiers

A phylogenetic analysis based on the 16S rRNA gene sequences was performed to examine the evolutionary relationship between ASVs classified as *Nitrospira* in this study and previously described *Nitrospira*. Sequences representing previously described *Nitrospira* were downloaded from NCBI, including the species representing comammox *Nitrospira*: *N. inopinata* (Daims et al., 2015) and *N. nitrificans* (Van Kessel et al., 2015). The sequences were aligned in R with the DECIPHER package (Wright, 2015) with default settings. Thereafter, phylogenetic relationships were inferred using a maximum likelihood (ML) tree constructed using phangorn (Schliep, 2011). Based on the AIC and BIC scores, the ML tree was inferred using the GTR + G and optimized with the TIM3 + G(4) model for sequence evolution as implemented in phangorn with default settings and 1,000 bootstraps (Schliep, 2011). The 16S rRNA gene sequences from two representative genera in the family *Nitrospiraceae* (*Thermodesulfobrevibrio* and *Leptospirillum*) were included and used as an outgroup to root the tree.

2.3.4. Processing of shotgun sequences and identification of *amoA* genes

In addition to 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, the DNA extracts of some samples were sent to Novogene, Germany for Illumina shotgun sequencing. Six samples from freshwater MBBF and three from brackish water MBBF, were selected. The raw data were filtered, and duplicate reads were removed with fastp v0.23.4 (Chen, 2023). The reads that mapped to the salmon or human genomes were removed with the Kneaddata tool v0.12.0 (<https://github.com/biobakery/kneaddata>). The ammonia monooxygenase subunit A (*amoA*) gene is known to be distinct among the nitrifier groups (AOA, AOB, and comammox) (Blom et al., 2024; Van Kessel et al., 2015). A strong correlation has been observed between quantitative PCR (qPCR) and metagenomic analysis in quantifying functional nitrification genes (Wang et al., 2014). To quantify the relative abundances of different groups of ammonia-oxidizing microorganisms within the biofilm communities, we created a database of *amoA* genes and their corresponding metadata by downloading all genomes from NCBI from genera representing ammonia oxidizers: *Nitrosomonas*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Nitrospira*, *Nitrosopumilus*, *Nitrosotalea*, *Nitrososphaera*, and the nitrite oxidizers: *Nitrocooccus*, *Nitrospira*, *Nitrospina*, and *Nitrobacter*. We excluded genomes with completeness below 75 % or contamination above 10 % based on analysis with CheckM v1.0.12 (Parks et al., 2015). We confirmed the taxonomy of the genomes using GTDB-Tk v2.4.0 (Chaumeil et al., 2022). Next, we annotated the genomes with Prokka 1.14.6 (Seemann, 2014) and extracted all *amoA* genes. We used MMseqs2 (Steinegger and Söding, 2017) to cluster the *amoA* genes at 99 % DNA similarity with settings “-cluster-mode 2 -cov-mode 1”. We mapped metagenomic shotgun sequencing reads to these representative *amoA* clusters using MMseqs2 easy-search and included hits with a minimum alignment of 50 base pairs and 80 % identity. The abundance was then normalized in

reads per kilobase per million reads (RPKM).

2.4. Data and statistical analyses

We used Hill's number 0 (observed ASV richness, S), 1 (exponential Shannon's entropy, exp. H'), and 2 (inverse Simpson, $1/D_s$) to express the alpha diversity of the communities. Using rarefied reads can bias the estimation of alpha diversity metrics, and using a measurement error model is encouraged (Willis, 2019). We therefore estimated diversity via error modeling using the iNEXT package (Hsieh et al., 2016). The rarefaction analysis with its extrapolation is provided in Supplementary File S3. Beta diversity was visualized using principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) plots based on the Bray–Curtis and Sørensen–Dice dissimilarity metrics calculated after rarefying read counts to 68,344. Differences in alpha diversity between sample groups were tested using Wilcoxon's test, while differences in community composition were tested using permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) based on the Bray–Curtis dissimilarity. Statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. All analyses were performed using the R programming language (R Core Team, 2024) in RStudio (Posit team, 2025). For data wrangling, transformation, and manipulation, the following packages were used: tidyverse (Wickham et al., 2019), phyloseq (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013), microViz (Barnett et al., 2021), Biostrings (Pagès et al., 2024), and tidytree (Yu, 2022). For statistical analysis, the following packages were used: rstatix (Kassambara, 2023), dunn.test (Dinno, 2024), vegan (Oksanen et al., 2025), and pairwiseAdonis (Martinez Arbizu, 2017). For data visualization and reporting, the following packages were used: ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggh4x (Brand, 2024), ggtree (Xu et al., 2022), ggpmisc (Aphalo, 2024), ggtext (Wilke and Wiernik, 2022), broom (Robinson et al., 2024), and cowplot (Wilke, 2024).

3. Results

3.1. Nitrification performance of biomedica in response to salinity changes

To evaluate the immediate tolerance of the brackish and seawater biofilters to abrupt and large salinity changes, the surface-specific ammonium removal capacity (SST) was estimated using batch reactors operated at salinities of 0, 15, and 31 ppt. Ammonium concentration decreased steadily, and nitrite levels remained near 0 mg/L during the test in all reactors (Fig. 2A), indicating that complete nitrification occurred at all tested salinities. The highest SST was estimated at 15 ppt salinity for the biomedica originating from the brackish biofilter with a reduction of 16 % and 22 % at 0 ppt and 31 ppt, respectively (Fig. 2B), indicating tolerance to abrupt salinity changes.

The highest SST was estimated at 31 ppt for biomedica originating from the seawater biofilter. An SST reduction of 8 % was estimated for the batch operated at 15 ppt, and a more pronounced reduction of 46 % was estimated at 0 ppt (Fig. 2B). Based on these estimates (Fig. 2B), the biomedica originating from the brackish biofilter appeared to be less affected when subjected to the abrupt salinity changes compared to those originating from the seawater biofilter, indicating that nitrifying communities in brackish biofilter possess broader salinity tolerance. Since these results were based on a single evaluation per salinity treatment, we could not determine the variation in salinity tolerance for each biomedica group and the numbers were reported as an estimate.

3.2. Temporal change in the biofilm community of Havland RAS biomedica

Next, we characterized the biofilm communities by sequencing 16S rRNA gene amplicons. The biofilm bacterial communities differed significantly between facilities, both in Bray–Curtis and Sørensen–Dice metrics (Fig. 3A, PERMANOVA, $p = 0.001$), indicating that both the taxa present and their relative abundances differed. We further investigated

Fig. 2. A) Scatter plots illustrating the changes of ammonium and nitrite concentrations over time in batch reactors operated at salinities of 0, 15, or 31 ppt. Linear regression lines are fitted to each plot. B) Surface-specific ammonium removal capacity ($\text{g N m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) of the bio-media from brackish biofilter (15 ppt) and seawater biofilter (35 ppt) tested in batch reactors at varying salinities. BW-BF = Brackish biofilter and SW-BF = Seawater biofilter.

the temporal change in the community structure of seawater biofilter bio-media across the transition from salmon to cod production. During this period, the observed ASV richness and exponential Shannon index increased over time, while the inverse Simpson index decreased (Fig. 3C), indicating that while the number of unique ASVs and the overall alpha diversity increased, the community became less even, suggesting a dominance of specific microbial taxa over time. We further explored the changes in their relative abundance at class level using a heatmap (Fig. 4A). The relative abundances of bacterial classes were altered following the transition from salmon to cod production, i.e., from the two first sampling times during the salmon production (April 24 and May 10) to the last two samplings during the cod production (Nov 16 and Nov 27) (Fig. 4A). The most notable changes were an increase in *Nitrospira* from 0.4 % to 14.6 % and a reduction in *Bacilli* from 19 % to 2.3 % (Fig. 4A). To a lesser extent, the relative abundances of *Saprospira*, *Deltaproteobacteria*, and *Cytophagia* increased, while *Planctomycetia*, *Gammaproteobacteria*, and *Acidimicrobiia* decreased (Fig. 4A).

Further, because the seawater biofilter was previously started using bio-media from the brackish biofilter, we explored whether these donor bio-media had influenced the community structure of the recipient biofilter. Over time, the biofilm community in the seawater biofilter (recipient) became increasingly similar to brackish biofilter (source) in terms of both taxa composition and relative abundance of taxa (Fig. 3B). At the two last samplings before transfer to cod production, on April 26 and May 10, their similarity to the biofilm community of the donor was relatively low, with average Bray–Curtis similarities of 0.22 and 0.23, respectively (Fig. 3B). After the transition to cod production, the Bray–Curtis similarity to the donor steadily increased, reaching 0.64 by November 27 (Fig. 3B). A similar pattern but with higher average similarities across all sampling dates was observed with the Sørensen–Dice similarity metric (Fig. 3B), indicating that the observed increase in similarity with time was mainly due to changes in relative abundances of the community populations.

3.3. Bacterial community compositions and diversity in biofilter-biofilm across RAS facilities

To examine potential differences in their nitrifying communities, we explored bacterial community composition in the brackish and seawater biofilter, including samples from the freshwater RAS producing Atlantic salmon smolt. The class-level community composition differed between the RAS facilities (Fig. 4A). In general, *Flavobacteriia*, *Gammaproteobacteria*, and *Bacilli* were present at higher relative abundances in the brackish biofilter compared to the freshwater biofilters (Fig. 4A). In contrast, the relative abundance of *Nitrospira* was substantially higher in the freshwater biofilter (32.4–37.8 %) than in the other biofilters, where the maximum of median value across different sampling date was only 14.9 % (PS_14.10) (Fig. 4A).

Analysis of alpha diversity metrics (Hill order number 0, 1, and 2) revealed significant differences in the bacterial biofilm communities between the RAS facilities (Fig. 4B). The bacterial biofilm communities from the freshwater RAS generally had the lowest values in all alpha diversity metrics (ASV richness, exponential Shannon, and inverse Simpson). This corroborates the observation of the dominance of a few ASVs classified to the class *Nitrospira* in these samples (Fig. 4B). Generally, biofilter-biofilm communities collected from high salinity RAS exhibited similar ASV richness, except those originating from the brackish biofilter operated at 22 ppt (Fig. 4B).

3.4. Nitrifying communities in freshwater, brackish, and seawater RAS

The finding that the bio-media from the brackish biofilter demonstrated a tolerance to salinity change prompted us to investigate the key nitrifiers in the communities. Both bacterial and archaeal communities were characterized separately, using PCR primer pairs targeting either the bacterial or the archaeal 16S rRNA genes. We identified ASVs assigned to taxa known to include nitrifiers (Fig. 5A). Nitrifiers

Fig. 3. A) PCoA based on Bray–Curtis and Sørensen–Dice dissimilarity metrics to compare bacterial biofilm communities among samples collected from brackish water and seawater biofilters. B) Similarity values of bacterial community in seawater biofilter-biofilm samples (recipient) collected on different dates (x-axis), before and after the transition from salmon to cod production (red arrow), compared to brackish biofilter-biofilm (donor; collected on Oct 14). C) Change in alpha diversity metrics (observed richness, exp. Shannon, and inverse Simpson) in the seawater biofilter community before and after the transition from salmon to cod production (indicated by the red arrow).

accounted for an average of 35.8 % of the total community in the freshwater RAS biofilter, which was considerably higher than the 10.5 % observed in brackish/seawater RAS (Fig. 5A). The genus *Nitrospira* dominated the nitrifying bacterial communities in the samples from the freshwater RAS, accounting for more than 86.4 % of the total nitrifier reads (Fig. 5A). However, representatives for AOB were rare and did not exceed a relative abundance of 11.6 % in any samples sequenced (averaged at 4.5 %). In the bacterial nitrifying communities from the brackish and seawater RAS, *Nitrospira* was the most abundant genus (average relative abundance: 65.5 %). However, there was also a significantly higher fraction of *Nitrosomonas* (AOB) (average of $31 \pm 19.8\%$) compared to freshwater RAS ($4.5 \pm 2.5\%$) (Fig. 5A). Other AOB taxa were observed in very low relative abundances in both brackish and freshwater samples (Fig. 5A). The genera *Nitrosophilus* and *Nitrobacter* were observed in the brackish and seawater RAS biofilters but not in the samples from the freshwater RAS. *Nitrospirillum* was absent in the samples from the brackish RAS while observed at very low relative abundances in freshwater (Fig. 5A).

Despite a high sequencing depth (median sequencing depth of 166,483 reads per sample) with a primer pair, more selective to archaea, archaeal community diversity in the biofilter-biofilm was remarkably low, even at the ASV level, i.e., most samples were dominated by a single ASV. Further, all archaeal ASVs detected were assigned to ammonia-oxidizing genera, with *Nitrosarchaeum* and *Nitrosopumilus* dominating

in freshwater and completely dominating the archaeal community of the samples, accounting for more than 94 % of the reads in most samples, except in the samples from the fixed-bed biofilter operated at 22 ppt, where the archaeal community was more diverse (Fig. 5B).

The low abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), such as *Nitrosospira* and *Nitrosomonas*, in freshwater RAS, combined with the predominance of *Nitrospira*, suggested that comammox *Nitrospira* (complete ammonia oxidizers) might play a role in ammonia oxidation within the system (Fig. 5A). To investigate this hypothesis, we performed a phylogenetic analysis to infer the relationships among the most abundant ASVs classified as *Nitrospira* identified in the samples from both the freshwater and brackish RAS in this study, alongside previously characterized *Nitrospira* species, including comammox representatives (Fig. 6).

The resulting phylogenetic tree showed that several *Nitrospira* ASVs from freshwater RAS (e.g., Zotu3, Zotu140, Zotu147, and Zotu155) were phylogenetically closer to the canonical nitrite-oxidizing *Nitrospira*, *N. defluvii* (Fig. 6). However, a subset of ASVs, including Zotu53, Zotu73, and Zotu149, were more closely related to the comammox species *N. nitrificans* (Fig. 6), supporting the potential presence of comammox *Nitrospira* within this RAS environment. In contrast, *Nitrospira* ASVs from brackish RAS (shown in green) formed a distinct clade (Fig. 6). They were closely related to seawater, canonical nitrite-oxidizing species such as *N. salsa* (e.g., Zotu9, Zotu12, Zotu15, Zotu103, and

Fig. 4. A) Heatmap showing bacterial community composition at the class level in biofilter-biofilm communities of RAS biofilters operated at varying salinities. Only classes with a minimum relative abundance of 2 % across all samples are displayed. B) Boxplot illustrating alpha diversity metrics of microbial communities in biofilter-biofilms from the RAS system with different salinities. FW = freshwater, BW = brackish water, SW = seawater RAS.

Zotu450) and *N. marina* (e.g., Zotu40) (Fig. 6).

3.5. Relative abundance of ammonia-oxidizers' *amoA* gene by shotgun sequencing

To identify the key ammonia oxidizers in the nitrifying biofilms, we quantified the relative abundances of AOB and AOA, and to differentiate between comammox and NOB *Nitrospira*, we analyzed a subset of the samples using shotgun sequencing. We characterized the diversity and relative abundances of the *amoA* gene variants (ammonia monooxygenase alpha subunit A), a key gene in ammonia oxidation.

The metagenomic samples contained diverse *amoA* gene variants within the AOB but were dominated by one of two variants representing *Nitrosomonas* in both the freshwater (*amoA_c052*) and brackish (*amoA_c186*) biofilter samples, with average relative abundances RPKM

of 34.9 % and 34.7 %, respectively (Fig. 7). In contrast to the amplicon sequencing results, shotgun sequencing revealed pronounced relative abundances (as *amoA* RPKM) of *Nitrosomonas* in freshwater and brackish biofilters (Fig. 7). The *amoA* genes representing comammox *Nitrospira* were only observed in freshwater RAS with a relative RPKM abundance of 25.2 %, while they were not observed in the samples from brackish RAS (Fig. 7).

The biofilm communities in the brackish RAS exhibited higher relative abundances of archaeal *amoA* gene variants (relative abundances of 47–50 %) compared to freshwater samples, which accounted for only 4 to 21 % (Fig. 7). In brackish samples, AOA and AOB showed an approximately 1:1 ratio of *amoA* RPKM (Fig. 7).

Fig. 5. A) The relative abundances of nitrifier genera in the nitrifying community based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing in the biofilter-biofilm sampled from freshwater (FW) and brackish and seawater (BW/SW) recirculating aquaculture systems. The results are expressed as a range from minimum to maximum, with the average value in brackets. The archaeal ASVs were excluded from the dataset generated using primers more selective for bacteria. Similarly, bacterial ASVs were excluded from the dataset generated using primers more selective for archaea. B) The relative abundances of the archaeal community in the biofilter-biofilm grouped at the ASV level.

4. Discussion

We aimed to improve the knowledge about the relationship between the nitrifying communities' composition at varying salinities and the salinity tolerance of biofilters in commercial RAS. The first objective was to examine the immediate tolerance of brackish and seawater biofilters to abrupt and large salinity changes. To achieve this, each biomedica group was tested in 0, 15, and 31 ppt salinity, which reflected a significant shift from their original salinity. The estimated SSTs for the brackish biofilters for all salinities tested were at the expected range for nitrifying biofilters of commercial RAS (Rusten et al., 2006). Our findings showed that although subjected to abrupt and large salinity changes, the biomedica showed a noticeable tolerance. For instance, the brackish biofilter retained around 78 % of its nitrification capacity after being subjected to an abrupt salinity change to 0 ppt. This value was higher than that reported in previous research with a similar salinity transition, e.g., around 50 % in Navada et al. (2020). Since the batch experiment was run in a single reactor for each salinity, running in replicates would strengthen the reproducibility of this salinity tolerance observation. Due to the abrupt nature of the salinity challenges and the assessment being performed after 24 h, the observed tolerance most likely reflected the physiological plasticity of the nitrifiers rather than a change in microbial composition. Further, we found that the brackish biofilter possessed a broader salinity tolerance. This observation aligns with previous studies suggesting that acclimation of biofilters to intermediate or brackish salinities could result in microbial communities with broader osmoregulation capacities, i.e., high physiological plasticity, in contrast to biofilters developed under either strict freshwater or full-strength seawater (Navada and Vadstein, 2022). We identified two dominant ammonia oxidizers in the brackish biofilter: *Nitrosomonas* (ammonia-oxidizing bacteria, AOB) and *Nitrosopumilus* (ammonia-

oxidizing archaea, AOA). From an ecophysiological perspective, AOA maintain relatively high activity in environments with high or fluctuating salinities (e.g., estuaries, salt marshes), significantly contributing to ammonia oxidation in these environments. In contrast, the AOB taxa have been found to exhibit narrower salinity tolerances and can be outcompeted by AOA (Jiang et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2021). This adaptability likely stems from unique, specialized cellular mechanisms of archaea for osmoregulation, such as osmolyte production, e.g., ectoine and betaine (Roberts, 2004). Therefore, we speculate that AOA were responsible for the relatively stable ammonia oxidation observed across varying salinity in our reactors.

The second objective was to evaluate the overall composition of RAS biofilters and the temporal dynamics of microbial communities during operational transitions. The freshwater biofilter exhibited significantly lower diversity than other biofilters. Although reduced diversity is often associated with instability or environmental perturbations (Infante-Villamil et al., 2021), selective enrichment of functionally important taxa can lead to lower diversity. In this study, the decline in alpha diversity in the freshwater biofilters primarily resulted from the dominance of *Nitrospira*, a key nitrifying taxon. The prevalence of *Nitrospira* suggests a stable and well-adapted community optimized for nitrification rather than dysbiosis. Therefore, interpreting alpha diversity metrics in microbial ecosystems should consider ecological function and community composition rather than relying solely on alpha diversity as an indicator of system health. We observed that over time, the microbial community in the recipient biofilter became increasingly similar to the donor biofilter. This trend suggests biofilter inoculation with established nitrifying biofilms can have long-lasting effects on microbial succession, particularly under stable environmental conditions like RAS. The trend also indicates that microbial seeding using biomedica can foster the establishment of robust nitrifying consortia. This strategy could be

Fig. 6. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree based on partial 16S rRNA gene sequences, illustrating the evolutionary relationships of major ASVs classified as *Nitrospira* in the samples. Previously published 16S rRNA gene sequences representing *Nitrospira*, including comammox *Nitrospira*, were included, and NCBI accession numbers were specified with the species name. Phylogenetic relationships were inferred using the GTR + G(4) model for sequence evolution, optimized with the TIM3 + G model as implemented in the R package phangorn (Schliep, 2011). Bootstrap support values from 1000 replicates are shown at the nodes. The tree is rooted with *Thermodesulfovibrio* as the outgroup. ASVs recovered from brackish and freshwater RAS were highlighted in green and red, respectively.

leveraged to optimize biofilter startup in commercial RAS. The increasing similarity of microbial communities between the seed and recipient biofilter may explain the underlying effective biofilter startup with microbial seeding found by a previous study (Zhu et al., 2016). The scientific literature describing this practice in RAS is limited.

The third objective was to describe the nitrifying community and to determine the relative contributions of AOB, AOA, and complete ammonia oxidizers (comammox *Nitrospira*) to ammonia oxidation under varying salinities using 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing and shotgun sequencing. Many other studies on RAS nitrifying communities based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing found that *Nitrospira*, presumably representing NOBs, dominated over AOB (Aalto et al., 2022; Dahle et al., 2023; Fossmark et al., 2021; Suurnäkki et al., 2020). However, our findings from shotgun sequencing suggest that the AOB genus *Nitrosomonas* plays a crucial role in ammonia oxidation in freshwater and brackish biofilters. This discrepancy likely arises from inherent limitations of 16S Illumina amplicon sequencing in accurately quantifying microbial taxa. Although widely used for microbial community profiling, the PCR amplification step introduces bias through variations in primer efficiency and template competition, potentially over- or underrepresenting specific taxa (Rintala et al., 2017). In contrast, shotgun sequencing targets the total genomic DNA without amplification bias, providing a more accurate representation of microbial community composition and relative abundances (Brumfield et al.,

2020). These findings underscore the need to carefully interpret 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing results when assessing the within-sample relative abundances of nitrifying communities in RAS biofilters.

Based on amplicon sequencing, we observed that the biofilter-biofilm community sampled from freshwater RAS contained a high fraction of nitrifiers, particularly *Nitrospira*, compared to the biofilters at the other locations. Further shotgun sequencing confirmed that a substantial fraction of the *Nitrospira* in the freshwater biofilters was comammox (more than 40 % of the *amoA* RPKM). The high relative abundance of nitrifiers, particularly comammox *Nitrospira*, in the biofilm communities of the freshwater RAS may be attributed to the position of the biofilters, which were located downstream of fixed-bed biofilters. Fixed-bed biofilters can reduce organic matter in the water (Fernandes et al., 2017), thereby reducing the competition between autotrophs and heterotrophs in the subsequent MBBF. The dominance of complete nitrification within a single organism (comammox) process rather than the conventional two-step nitrification process (AOB + NOB) is often observed in environments with consistently low ammonia concentrations, such as oligotrophic waters (e.g., drinking water, lakes) (Wang et al., 2017), including RAS (Bartelme et al., 2017), where total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) levels are maintained below 2 mg/L. Selection for comammox likely reflects their competitive advantage of having a higher substrate affinity (lower K_m), allowing them to outcompete AOB under low-ammonia conditions (Ghimire-Kafle et al., 2024; Jung et al.,

Fig. 7. Heatmap showing the relative abundance of *amoA* genes (calculated as the relative abundance of all *amoA* mapping reads found; see Methods section) from different ammonia-oxidizing groups (AOA, AOB, and comammox) in the moving-bed biofilter-biofilm of freshwater and brackish RAS. Colour intensity reflects relative abundance, with darker red indicating higher levels. Metagenomic reads were mapped to the representative sequence of each *amoA* gene variant clustered at 99 % identity, where each cluster was identified by names such as *amoA_c189*, *amoA_c107*, etc. The suffix number after the sample name indicates the replicate. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2022). In the shotgun sequencing dataset, we did not observe the presence of comammox *amoA* in brackish and seawater biofilters, aligning with a global distribution study of comammox performed by Palomo et al. (2022). Comammox organisms are principally defined by their ability to oxidize ammonia and nitrite within a single cell. However, no high-quality genome recovered from the marine environment has been found to contain the complete set of genes responsible for both nitrification steps. Consequently, inferring the absence/presence of comammox in marine environments based on marker genes, e.g., *amoA*, is challenging. The absence of *amoA* comammox in this study cannot be used to nullify the potential presence of comammox in the marine environment. Marine comammox may have distinct *amoA* genes; therefore, they are not detected by mapping their *amoA* gene to the database created from freshwater comammox species exclusively from the *Nitrospira* genus. Nevertheless, some studies have reported the presence of comammox based on qPCR with *amoA* as a marker gene assumed to be specific to comammox, e.g., in Sun et al. (2020) or based on taxonomic classification based on partial 16S rRNA gene from the amplicon sequencing, as in Liu et al. (2023). Their findings need further validation as the actual existence of marine comammox can only be fully

confirmed by genomic evidence.

Our findings suggest that AOA were found at high relative abundance in the high salinity biofilter (around 50 % of the *amoA* genes RPKM) and were also observed in the freshwater biofilter, although at lower abundances. However, they occurred with low diversity, dominated by the genera *Nitrosarchaeum* and *Nitrosopumilus*, respectively. Our findings contrasted with previous studies, which reported negligible archaeal contributions to ammonia oxidation in freshwater, brackish, and seawater biofilters. For instance, 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing and electron microscopy (Hüpeden et al., 2020) analyses did not find archaea in the biofilters, suggesting a limited role in such systems. Additionally, Roalkvam et al. (2020) demonstrated that the relative abundance of ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA) within RAS biofilm biomedica declined over time and was replaced by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), even though the biofilter had initially been inoculated with a substantial fraction of AOA 1.5 years before sampling. We noted that the discrepancies can be attributed to several factors: 1) the universality and specificity of the PCR primers used for archaea, 2) the significantly higher ammonia concentrations tested in some studies, and 3) the inherent limitations of Illumina 16S rRNA gene amplicon

sequencing in accurately quantifying bacterial cell abundance. The high abundance of AOA, as shown in their relative *amoA* RPKM in this study, aligns with the results from qPCR analysis on samples from freshwater biofilters such as Bartelme et al. (2017) and Khangembam et al. (2017) and marine RAS (Brown et al., 2013).

Previous studies have shown that AOA were more abundant, out-competing the AOB, in the environment with low TAN available per bacteria number due to their higher substrate affinity (Km) and flexible reaction kinetics (Hatzenpichler, 2012). An extensive comparative study of ammonium oxidizers (Jung et al., 2022) showed that all characterized AOA (except for representatives of the genus *Nitrosocosmicus*) and the comammox bacterium *N. inopinata* possess much higher affinity for total ammonium, 10–3000 times higher than the AOB *N. oceanii* or *N. europaea*, indicating their high competitiveness in ammonia-limited environments. Given this, AOA may have also contributed substantially to ammonia oxidation in low-ammonia environments such as Norwegian salmon RAS farms, where TAN levels are strictly regulated and maintained below 2 mg/L. Meanwhile, its counterpart, the AOB, are typically much more dominant in ammonia-rich environments, such as wastewater treatment plants (Gao et al., 2014; Yin et al., 2018). Interestingly, although the fresh and marine RAS biofilters examined in this study generally had low TAN concentrations, the former appeared to be more selective for comammox and the latter for AOA. Comammox has not been found and probably is not adapted for living in marine environments, as evidenced by its reduced activity in the saline conditions (Jiang et al., 2023). AOA are known to be better adapted to high salinity (Wang et al., 2023); therefore, they have greater importance in ammonia oxidation in marine environments than freshwater systems. This study adds evidence to the limited documentation on the importance of archaea to nitrification in the RAS biofilter.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates a noticeable tolerance of nitrifying biofilters operated at brackish salinity (15 ppt) to abrupt and significant salinity changes from freshwater (0 ppt) to seawater (31 ppt), with reductions in nitrification capacity of 16 % and 22 %, respectively. We found that microbial seeding with mature biofilter biomedica has a long-lasting effect on biofilter maturation. The ammonia-poor condition in RAS appears to select for microbes with high affinities to ammonia, such as AOA and comammox *Nitrospira*. Nitrifying communities in RAS biofilters operated at higher salinity had higher relative abundances of AOA (approximately 50 % of the *amoA* gene RPKM) compared to the freshwater RAS (ranging from 4 % to 21 %). This contrasts with previous

reports of the limited abundance of AOA in RAS biofilters. The archaeal communities in RAS biofilters showed low diversity, dominated by *Nitrosarchaeum* (freshwater) and *Nitrosopumilus* (seawater). On the other hand, comammox *Nitrospira* was highly abundant in the nitrifying community of freshwater RAS moving-bed biofilters, where it accounted for as much as around 45 % of the *amoA* RPKM, but was not detected in the brackish system.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fernando Fernando: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Simen Fredriksen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Eirik Degré Lorentsen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Line Moen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ingrid Bakke:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Composition of ammonium medium

Table A.1
Chemical composition of the ammonium medium (concentration of 7.5 mg/L) used for determining the ammonia removal rate.

Chemical	Quantity (g/L)
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.03540
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.272
Na ₂ CO ₃	0.2
Trace metal solution	10 mL of stock solution
pH adjustment	3–6 drops of HCl to pH 7.5

Table A.2
Chemical composition of the trace metal solution.

Chemical	Quantity (g/L)
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	2.5
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1.5
FeCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.2
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.55
ZnCl ₂	0.07
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.12
NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.12
EDTA; Tridriplex III	2.8

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.743280>.

Data availability

Raw sequencing data are available on NCBI with an accession ID of PRJNA1274364. The raw data related to the nitrification capacity assessment are provided in the Supplementary File S1. The metadata for each sequencing library, describing the sampling location, salinity, primers, and other relevant information, is provided in Supplementary File S2.

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